

FACTORS AFFECTING PERSONALITY FORMATION

Shakhrinoz Tursunova Matniyozovna

Bukhara State University Faculty of Foreign Languages
Philology and language teaching (English) 4th stage student

ABSTRACT

This article provides information about personality and factors influencing its formation.

Key words: Person, psychology, behavior, society, historical period, profession, social work.

INTRODUCTION

A person's living conditions, in other words, the social environment that surrounds him, is a legal process, so the problem of personality and its study will always remain one of the most pressing problems for social psychology as well as all other sciences. Problems no matter how similar they are, they always remain the problems of a person who lives in different historical conditions, in a changed social environment, and therefore has a different way of thinking and feels and understands the world differently. Person Being a biological type, it is also a child of a certain historical period and social environment in a certain country. Depending on which historical period and social environment a person lives in, there will be serious changes in his character. Supporters of social theory also recognize that there are innate (hereditary) characteristics in a person's character and behavior. but according to them, these characteristics in a person are mainly acquired in a certain social environment (family, educational and work team, spirit of the times, state structure, professional and creative associations, etc.) and through work, language, speech, education, experience in the formation and historical development of the individual and society, the change of social work, the way of speech and thinking, and the improvement of family-marriage relations were of great importance. It ensures that a person becomes a human being, that is, a socialized being. As a result of social influence on genetically limited natural factors, the duration of human life increases. A person with a body structure that allows him to work biologically becomes a person - a subject that develops under the influence of the social environment, communicates with other people using language, knows reality and changes assets. The theory of a person's belonging to the human gender is represented by the concept of an individual. A person born as an individual later becomes a person.[1] The process of assimilation of social experience

of a person takes place in the process of interaction of a person with others and has a great influence on the formation of his "inner world". Being active in a person is manifested in his characteristic behavioral motives, instructions and methods of following them. It is a concrete living person with his strengths and weaknesses, which was created as a result of upbringing. The activity of a person is expressed in his choice of a path for his life, in his occupation of this path, and even in his understanding of his position and place. . One of the most characteristic aspects of human personality is its individuality. Individuality includes character, temperament, characteristics of the development of mental processes, a set of dominant emotions, motivations for activity, and abilities. is the result of the changes that occur in the activity, and is primarily related to social education. There are a number of theories of personality formation in psychology, which approach the study of the human personality from different points of view and shed light on the nature of the problem in different ways.[2] We can give examples of biogenetic, sociogenetic, psychogenetic, cognitivist, psycho-analytic, behaviorist and similar theories. Below we will get acquainted with these theories and some of them. In the biogenetic theory, the biological development of a person is considered as the main factor, and the development of other processes is dependent on this factor. According to this theory, biological determinants are the basis of personality formation, and social-psychological characteristics also develop depending on them. We give information about the sociogenetic theory, taking into account that the views of the supporters of the biogenetic theory on the factors affecting the formation of personality are covered in the textbooks "General psychology" and "Psychology of youth periods", and that it is appropriate to talk about the role of social factors in social psychology. Biogenetic The opposite of the theory is the sociogenetic theory.[3] In this theory, the changes that occur in a person are explained on the basis of the structure of society, the methods of socialization, and the means of interaction with the surrounding people. It is emphasized that he becomes a person under the secret. One of the most important theories that emerged in the West as one of the theories of social direction is the theory of roles. According to this theory, society has created a complex of stable methods of behavior called status (rights) for each of its members, in which the behavior that a person exhibits in society through the special roles that a person must perform in the social environment. character and his relationship with others clearly shows what kind of person he is. As one of the theories of social direction, the theory of knowledge acquisition (accustoming) in individual experience and personal socialization is widespread in the United States, and according to this theory, the life of a person and it is mentioned that it depends on the stability of the factors affecting the attitude to the reality in the environment, the acquisition of skills and the assimilation of the acquired knowledge.[4]

DISCUSSION AND RESULT

We can see that the above-mentioned theories do not provide detailed information about the socio-historical and objective conditions of human life. Sociogenetic theory considers the development of a person to be the result of the direct influence of the surrounding social environment. According to sociogeneticists, a person is “a copy of the social environment.” Sociogeneticists, like biogeneticists, deny the individual activity of the developing person. A person is called a being who only adapts to the surrounding environment and plays a passive role. Understanding the laws of personality development cannot be based on either the biogenetic theory or the sociogenetic theory. In the words of the foreign psychologist K. Mark, it cannot be disputed that the essence of the human personality consists of the sum of all social relations. Being a social being, a person retains the signs of a natural, biological structure.

CONCLUSION

Society limits a person in many ways, "censors" his instincts and inclinations. As a result, a person is forced to restrain himself, not to make unavoidable mistakes, to curb his emotional experiences. The dependence of the person on the environment is given priority. In this case, the individual emerges as a simple function of the social environment, which is automatically determined by the environment. The environment transfers its most important qualities to the person. They become forms of personal activity. One of the theories of personality formation in psychology is the psychogenetic approach, which, without disparaging biogenetic and sociogenetic factors, emphasizes that the development of mental processes of a person is of primary importance. we can call a person. First of all, a person is born as an individual, then he becomes a person under the influence of social relations. Personality formation is manifested in various activities aimed at changing the reality in the surrounding society. A person's interaction with society is expressed in his choice of the path necessary for his life and in his full occupation of the chosen path.

REFERENCES:

1. V. Karimova. Social psychology and practice. — Tashkent- 2009. [1]
- 2.V. Karimova, O. Khaitov. The issue of socialization of the person. - Tashkent-2007.[2]
3. Smelzer N.I. Sociology. — Moscow- 1994.[3]
4. www.ziyonet.uz. [4]